

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Intergenerational Child Mortality Impacts of Deworming: Experimental Evidence from Two Decades of the Kenya Life Panel Survey"

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Charlotte Lane

Published on: Oct 08, 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.33a621b6>

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: “Intergenerational Child Mortality Impacts of Deworming: Experimental Evidence from Two Decades of the Kenya Life Panel Survey”^[1]. The authors find evidence for an intergenerational mortality benefit that could be large enough to make a difference to the debate over the effectiveness of deworming (relative to other impactful interventions like bednets). The evaluators generally find the paper credible, but raise some concerns (e.g., about consistency with the pre-analysis plan) and request some robustness checks. The authors responded briefly, noting they are revising the paper in response to these and other comments. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Anonymous Evaluation 1](#)
2. [Anonymous Evaluation 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	87	3.5
Evaluator 2	90	4.5

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.⁴

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

A well-written and coherent paper. One of the first showing intergenerational effects of childhood health intervention in [a] LMIC, including cost-benefit analysis. Statistical power calculation not provided. Literature review is slightly one-sided. Some results in tables could be discussed further in text. Some typical outcomes [were] not present (nor mentioned), [... and] if [they] exist in the data [it] would be interesting to see them.

Anonymous evaluator 2

This is a highly credible and important analysis of the intergenerational effects of a Kenyan deworming intervention. Such effects are important to document because they could meaningfully affect the cost-benefit analysis of such programs and also teach us about the mechanisms through which parents transmit advantage to their children. However, the analysis would be more credible if the authors were transparent about their deviations from the pre-analysis plan, which include the addition of (and exclusion of) outcomes and changes to the empirical specification. Also, more information on the “first stage”—the impact of randomization on receipt of deworming treatment—would be helpful.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2⁵		
	Anonymous		Anonymous		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁶	87	(77, 97)	90	(80, 100)	
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁷			90	(80, 100)	8
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁹	85	(75, 95)	80	(70, 90)	10

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹¹	85	(75, 95)	85	(75, 95)	12
Logic & communication ¹³	85	(75, 95)	95	(90, 100)	14
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁵	85	(75, 95)	90	(80, 100)	16
Real-world relevance ¹⁷	95	(90, 100)	95 ¹⁸	(90, 100)	19
Relevance to global priorities ²⁰	95	(90, 100)	95 ²¹	(90, 100)	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous		Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	3.5	(3.0, 4.0)	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	3.5	(3.0, 4.0)	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Unjournal process notes

Why we chose this paper

From the prioritization assessor

This paper has the potential to be highly influential and very important.

Some concerns were raised about potential lack of vetting or replication.

There is substantial debate over the effectiveness of deworming relative to other impactful interventions like bednets. Evidence for the effectiveness of deworming seems to be far more uncertain with much greater confidence intervals than for other interventions. Previous work, particularly that focusing on the long-term impact, seems to be inconsistent, or in some cases seemed face-value implausible. See fairly non-technical discussions:

[GiveWell's updated estimate of deworming and decay — EA Forum](#)

<https://www.vox.com/future-perfect/2022/7/19/23268786/deworming-givewell-effective-altruism-michael-hobbes>

And GiveWell's recommendation change: [Evidence Action's Deworm the World Initiative – August 2022 version](#)

More evidence and more synthesis, and more careful scrutiny would seem to be high value; the magnitude of the estimates of the impact of deworming, and our confidence in these estimates seems pivotal to driving charitable funding and intervention recommendations.

The intergenerational mortality benefit seems substantial enough in magnitude to make a difference as confirmed by the paper authors, and by a very quick chat GPT-assisted back-of-the-envelope calculation and review. (See [here](#), may contain errors, not checked.)

Evaluation process

This evaluation process took longer than normal/desirable. We prioritized this for evaluation on Dec. 18, 2023. The initially assigned evaluation manager was overloaded, and we needed to change. We commissioned three evaluations, one of which did not meet our standards for posting (lack of detail, some misunderstandings). We also had some delays in finding relevant evaluators in this area.

The authors engaged with this process, sharing a brief response (linked in this package), and suggesting that they intend to respond further as a new version of the paper is released. We allowed the evaluators to adjust their content to this response. E2 modified their report very slightly, but neither evaluator chose to change their ratings.

References

1. Kremer, M., Luby, S., Maertens, R., Tan, B., & Więcek, W. (2023). Water Treatment and Child Mortality: A Meta-analysis and Cost-effectiveness Analysis. NBER Working Paper No. 30835.
<https://doi.org/10.3386/w30835>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)
2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
4. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. [↵](#)
5. This evaluator used a slightly different (newer) evaluation form; see notes below. [↵](#)
- 6.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

7. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

8. The randomized design makes the results highly credible [↵](#)

9.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

10. This paper makes a strong advancement, although other papers suggest such intergenerational effects were likely [↵](#)

11. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

12. Changes from pre-analysis plan should be noted [↵](#)

13. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

14. Very well-written and clear [↵](#)

15.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

16. The authors have posted the data: <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataverse/KLPS> [↵](#)

17.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

⇐

18.

The latter ratings were merged in the new form, which Eval. 2 used.

”Are the paper’s chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?”

“Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?” ⇐

19. Highly relevant ⇐

20. Are the paper’s chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? ⇐

21.

The latter ratings were merged in the new form, which Eval. 2 used.

”Are the paper’s chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?”

“Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?” ⇐

References

1. Walker, M., Huang, A., Asman, S., Baird, S., Fernald, L., Hicks, J. H., ... Miguel, E. (2023). *Intergenerational Child Mortality Impacts of Deworming: Experimental Evidence from Two Decades of the Kenya Life Panel Survey*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31162> ⇐